

Factors to Consider in Developing a Biodiversity Monitoring Plan for Conservation

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P.J. Stephenson^{1,2}

To explain key factors that need to be considered when developing effective and cost-efficient plans for monitoring biodiversity in the context of conservation projects.

› Introduction

Assessing the progress of a conservation project needs to be based on a well-designed, goal-driven monitoring and evaluation plan. Suitable indicators need to be selected that address the project's goals and the questions that the project team needs to answer (e.g., Have the project objectives been delivered? How has natural habitat changed? Have target species populations recovered?). Then, based on those indicators, relevant monitoring methods need to be chosen and applied. This guide explains the key steps required and factors to consider in developing such a monitoring plan. Key references and resources to expand on the topics covered are listed at the end of the document.

1 IUCN SSS Species Monitoring Specialist Group

2 Laboratory for Conservation Biology, Department of Ecology & Evolution, University of Lausanne, CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland; stephensonpj@gmail.com

› Elements of a Goal-based Monitoring Plan

Effective monitoring programmes address well-defined questions, are underpinned by rigorous statistical design, and are relevant for management. To meet those needs, a monitoring plan needs to be developed based around a project's goals, objectives and outputs and using relevant data collection protocols.

Good planning is a pre-requisite for good monitoring. So conservation projects first need to set clear and measurable goals and objectives (using processes such as those described in CMP, 2025), before then developing a monitoring plan.

Following best practices, a monitoring plan generally includes:

- ♦ **Indicators** - “What” the project will measure;
- ♦ **Methods** - “How” the indicators will be measured (which may include the type of tool to be used or the databases from which secondary data will be sourced);
- ♦ **Timing and frequency** - “When” the indicators will be measured;
- ♦ **Roles and responsibilities** - “Who” will measure the indicators;
- ♦ **Location** - “Where” the indicators will be measured.

Project teams will also need to plan how and where they will store data, what analyses to perform, and how to share data and results. Monitoring plans should preferably be developed in collaboration with partners, which can facilitate discussions and agreement on data ownership and sharing. Synergies should also be sought wherever possible with national, regional and global monitoring schemes so that data can be useful and valued beyond the scope of the project.

› Choosing Indicators

In most cases, suitable state indicators will be used to measure the impact of a project's biodiversity goal on target species and habitats. Benefit indicators can be used when a project has human wellbeing goals or wants to demonstrate how ecosystem services contribute to people's needs. Pressure indicators will measure project objectives (outcomes) focused on alleviating threats, and response indicators will measure progress on project activities and strategies (outputs). This state-pressure-response-benefit indicator framework has been adopted by many conservation organisations and is used by United Nations agencies and member states to monitor global goals, such as the Sustainable Development Goals and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF).

State and benefit indicators answer questions such as:

- ♦ Have project goals been attained and what were the main impacts at the individual project level? (e.g., to what extent was biodiversity state improved?)
- ♦ How were target groups and indirect beneficiaries impacted by the project? (e.g., to what extent were community livelihoods or access to key facilities improved?)

Pressure indicators answer questions such as:

- ♦ Have project objectives been attained and what were the main outcomes at the individual project level? (e.g., has habitat loss or poaching been reduced?)

Response indicators answer questions such as:

- ♦ How well did projects achieve what they set out to achieve?
- ♦ Which responses (actions, strategies) worked well or less well?

BOX 1. SOME EXAMPLES OF TYPES OF INDICATORS

State: Habitat cover or extent; Habitat fragmentation or connectivity; Water quality (extent and condition of surface freshwater); Water quantity and flow; Species presence (or occurrence or occupancy or range; especially threatened species); Species abundance (absolute or relative); Species richness/diversity.

Benefits: Abundance of species used sustainably by local communities; Abundance of pollinator species; Volume of harvest of sustainably used resources (e.g., fish, timber); Water quality; Air quality; Soil quality; Income generated from natural resources managed sustainably.

Pressures: Habitat loss by type of land use change (e.g. agriculture, mining, roads); Habitat fragmentation; Extent of infrastructure/built environment; Number of animals killed or plants and fungi logged or collected; Number of incidents of illegal or damaging activity, disaggregated by cause (e.g. hunting, fishing, logging, mining); Level of wildlife trade; Levels of pollutants in air, water or soil; Number of pollution incidents (e.g., spills; discharges); Presence/abundance of invasive alien species; Volume of water abstracted; Environmental flows; Fire frequency and extent; Extent of coral bleaching.

Responses: Number of direct or indirect beneficiaries (e.g., number of local people employed in conservation work); Number of people trained and using their training; Infrastructure (e.g., ranger posts, ecotourism facilities) constructed and used; Area set aside for natural regeneration; Number and species of organisms introduced/planted for restoration; Survivorship of introduced/planted organisms; Number/area of invasive alien species removed; Area protected (e.g., size of protected and conserved area); Proportion of habitat protected; Protected area management effectiveness; Proportion of area under sustainable management; Number of law enforcement patrols; Number of arrests per unit law enforcement effort; Proportion of local farmers setting aside native forest or adopting agroforestry/sustainable forest management practices; Number of Indigenous People's governance bodies and/or processes recognized by relevant government departments; Proportion of Indigenous People and local communities with clearly defined rights to manage their own natural resources.

Key criteria for good indicators are often described as being SMART - specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and timebound. In particular, indicators should be:

- ♦ Scientifically credible, using methods that have been well-tested, preferably peer-reviewed in the scientific literature, and with evidence that change in the indicator represents change in the pressure, state, response or benefit being measured;
- ♦ Feasible to apply in the context of the project's goals, capacity and budget for the biomes, habitats and species concerned;
- ♦ Measurable, in quantitative or qualitative terms;
- ♦ Precise, so that they are defined the same way by everyone who uses them;
- ♦ Understandable, so that everyone who is concerned by the results can interpret what they mean.

Many projects will find it useful to use at least a handful of indicators linked to national, regional or global indicator sets (such as the indicators for the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (CBD, 2022) or SDGs (UN Statistics Division, 2025) to help demonstrate the project's contribution to national efforts.

As a rule of thumb, the ideal number of indicators necessary for a project can be defined as "the minimum number that answers the question: has the goal or objective been achieved?" (World Bank, 2004).

› Choosing Methods

Numerous methods are available for collecting biodiversity data, from a range of direct observation techniques, such as transect walks and dives, point counts and quadrats, to technological tools, such as satellite-based remote sensing, camera traps and bioacoustics (Fig. 1). The methods used to collect data need to be chosen based on a range of factors, such as the metrics and indicators being measured, the scale of the monitoring, the habitats and species being surveyed, the available resources, and the goal of the data collection exercise.

Key questions to consider in choosing data collection methods therefore include:

- ♦ What metrics and indicators need to be measured?
- ♦ Are there any data available in national, regional or global databases or papers and reports that may provide an existing baseline or trends?
- ♦ What are the pros and cons of available data collection methods against each metric or indicator?
- ♦ Can any information be derived from interviews with key informants, including Indigenous People or local communities?
- ♦ What capacity and resources are available to support data collection and does this favour or restrict certain methods?

Future *Biodiversity Monitoring Guidance Notes* will be dedicated to discussing the key methods used, including direct human observations, satellite-based remote sensing, cameras and camera traps, acoustic recording devices, and environmental DNA.

Figure 1. Methods to collect biodiversity are numerous and need to be chosen carefully.

› Survey Design

The use of established protocols will help ensure appropriate sampling. For example, several monitoring methods based around transects (e.g., walked transects, aerial or vessel-based surveys, camera trapping) can measure species presence-absence or occupancy, and their association with habitats, as well as relative or absolute abundance of some species, if appropriate protocols (e.g., TEAM Network, 2011a,b) and distance sampling methods (e.g., Buckland *et al.*, 2015) are applied. Such standardized approaches also ensure that surveys take account of differing levels of detectability of different species in different habitats. Several protocols highlight the minimum number of observations needed to detect change based on relevant statistical power analyses.

Occupancy modelling (Welsh *et al.*, 2013 ; Bailey *et al.*, 2014; MacKenzie *et al.*, 2017) can be used to improve estimates of occupancy by correcting for the probability of a missed detection when the species is present. To this end, various free software packages are available to help account for differing levels of detectability in species occurrence, abundance and richness, such as [PRESENCE](#) and [spOccupancy](#) for occupancy, [DISTANCE](#) for distance sampling, [MARK](#) for capture-recapture and occupancy modelling, and [SPECRICH](#) for species richness.

It is important to choose appropriate statistical approaches to allow correct inferences about change, including independent sampling and random transect selection (Yoccoz *et al.*, 2001; Reynolds, 2013; Buckland *et al.*, 2015). The use of counterfactuals (measuring the same indicator in a similar situation where the project did not intervene) is the strongest way of measuring the impact of an intervention against a control scenario, with BACI (before-after control-impact) design and BAC (before-after control) approaches often recommended (Stephenson, 2021; Wauchope *et al.*, 2021). Counterfactuals are encouraged specifically for larger and longer-term projects which should be investing more in monitoring. Many restoration projects will have identified reference sites and these can be monitored to gauge progress against project goals (Mansourian & Stephenson, 2023).

› Data Standards, Data Management and Data Sharing

Well-managed and easily accessible data are a pre-requisite for effective monitoring and to ensure that information flows to decision-makers. Therefore, protocols need to be established for collecting, recording, documenting, storing and archiving data, and best practices followed on metadata and data custodianship, ownership and access.

The main decisions to be made on data management (sensu Convention on Wetlands, 2025) include:

- ♦ Which data management standards or protocols will be followed?
- ♦ Where will the data be stored and how? When will it be archived, and is there an expiry date to storage and archiving?
- ♦ How frequently will the data be updated?
- ♦ How will the data be analyzed and visualized?
- ♦ How will the data be structured in reporting to respond to multiple reporting frameworks, and ensure consistency to facilitate comparability and trend analysis?

The use of standards and protocols for collecting and managing data will help ensure data are consistent, high quality, meaningful and useful. In addition to data collection protocols specific to certain indicators or tools, there are general data standards available that provide the shared rules and conventions to describe, record and structure datasets that facilitate data management, sharing and citation.

These are numerous biodiversity data standards (Biodiversity Information Standards, 2020) but three of the most commonly used (GBIF, 2025) are:

- ♦ The Darwin Core Standard - a stable, straightforward and flexible framework for compiling biodiversity data from varied and variable sources.
- ♦ Ecological Metadata Language or EML - a metadata standard that records information about ecological datasets in a series of modular and extensible XML document types.
- ♦ BioCAsE Access to Biological Collections Data (ABCD) data exchange standard – developed by the Biological Collection Access Service (BioCAsE), an international network linking biological collections data from natural history museums, botanical and zoological gardens, and research institutions.

Project data should be shared wherever possible³ so that it can be used by other stakeholders and help contribute to national, regional or global biodiversity monitoring efforts. This can be done by ensuring all reports and publications include data as supplementary material, and by directly contributing data to databases (Box 2).

Project teams will often share lessons and disseminate stories and information with partners and other interested stakeholders through a variety of communications channels, including blog posts, social media, traditional media, newsletters, and papers in relevant scientific journals. Having reliable monitoring data to demonstrate change will greatly enrich these communications.

BOX 2. SOME PLACES TO SHARE DATA

Several global data repositories and platforms are available for specific monitoring methods, such as [Global Forest Watch](#) for satellite forest data, [Wildlife Insights](#) and [eMammal](#) for camera trap data, and [ARBIMON](#) and [REAL](#) for acoustic data.

Examples of method-agnostic global databases of note that projects could consider sharing data with include:

- ♦ Data on species presence could be shared with the Global Biodiversity Information Facility ([GBIF](#));
- ♦ Data on species population trends could be shared with the [Living Planet Index](#);
- ♦ Data on protected area management effectiveness could be shared with the [Global Database on Protected Area Management Effectiveness](#);
- ♦ Data on species abundance, distribution and threats could be shared with relevant IUCN Species Survival Commission Specialist Groups to contribute to Red List assessments and updates of the [IUCN Red List of Threatened Species](#).

³ In some cases, data may be too sensitive to share (e.g., the locations of highly threatened species).

› Capacity and Partnerships to Implement the Monitoring Plan

Technical and institutional capacity, adequate funding, and a willingness to use and share data in project management, are key enabling conditions for effective monitoring. Therefore, project teams will need to ensure they set aside an appropriate proportion of their budget and their human resources for monitoring. This will include ensuring they have the expertise and the means to conduct relevant data collection, as well as to track and report on project progress in all activities. In many cases, this capacity may need to be outsourced to suitable partners who can help collect data or extract it from existing databases.

Many projects will want to engage local stakeholders in monitoring as this can help facilitate both data collection and use. Local communities, local, national or global civil society organisations and NGOs, and academic and research institutions are often suitable monitoring partners in conservation projects. It is increasingly recognised (e.g., UNEP, 2019; McElwee *et al.* 2020; Jennings *et al.* 2023) that Indigenous and local knowledge is of equal value to formal scientific knowledge and can enrich our understanding of nature and ecosystem services. Indigenous People and local communities should therefore be involved in biodiversity monitoring schemes wherever possible.

› Using Data, Learning and Adapting

People are less likely to be willing to use biodiversity data when the data are difficult to interpret, so data providers and data users need to collaborate on producing data-derived products in formats, such as graphs, dashboards, maps or infographics, that facilitate interpretation and aid decision-making. Satellite-based remote sensing data are usually presented as maps. It should also be feasible to convert the images and sounds captured by Earth-based sensors, such as cameras or acoustic recording devices, into visual, easy-to-interpret formats to complement graphs of indicator trends.

Project teams need to set aside time specifically to discuss and act on monitoring data, during formal and informal meetings. Monitoring results should be on the agenda regularly for all relevant governance bodies of the organisations involved in the project so as to facilitate adaptive management.

The review of results should also be used to determine if the monitoring system is delivering. If any indicators are not working or methods are not providing the data needed, the indicator or the method should be changed as early possible in the project's implementation.

Ultimately, if project teams and their partners can follow simple best practices for the participatory monitoring of biodiversity states, pressures, responses and benefits, and take account of some of the issues highlighted in this guidance, we can hope to see more impactful conservation for the benefit of people and nature.

References Cited and Key Resources and Links on Topics Covered

> Global indicator sets

- CBD, 2022. *Decision Adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity at its Fifteenth Meeting, Part II. Monitoring framework for the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.* CBD/COP/DEC/15/5 19 December 2022. [🔗](#)
- United Nations Statistics Division, 2025. *Global indicator framework for the Sustainable Development Goals and targets of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, after 2025 review.* [🔗](#)

> Guidelines for developing monitoring plans and choosing indicators (conservation and development projects)

- Biodiversity Indicators Partnership, 2025. *What makes a successful indicator?* [🔗](#)
- Brown, C., Reyers, B., Ingwall-King, L., Mapendembe, A., Nel, J., et al., 2014. *Measuring Ecosystem Services: Guidance on developing ecosystem service indicators.* United Nations Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre, Cambridge, UK. [🔗](#)
- CMP - Conservation Measures Partnership, 2025. *Open Standards for the Practice of Conservation. Version 5.* Bethesda, USA: CMP. [🔗](#)
- Convention on Wetlands 2025. *Guidance for Implementing a Structured Process for National Wetland Inventory. Version 1.0.* (P.J. Stephenson, I. Dronova, D. Friess, C.M. Finlayson & F. Lafaye de Micheaux). Secretariat of the Convention on Wetlands, Gland, Switzerland. [🔗](#)
- del Pozo, M.S., Body, G., Rerig, G. and Basille, M., 2023. *Guide on Harmonising Biodiversity Monitoring Protocols Across Scales.* Biodiversa+ report. 60 pp. [🔗](#)
- Dickson, I.M., Butchart, S.H.M., Dauncey, V., Hughes, J., Jefferson, R., et al. 2017. PRISM – Toolkit for evaluating the outcomes and impacts of small/medium-sized conservation projects. Version 1. Cambridge Conservation Initiative, Cambridge, UK. [🔗](#)
- FAO and WRI, 2024. *AURORA: Assessment, Understanding and Reporting of Restoration Actions.* [🔗](#)
- Likens, G. and Lindenmayer, D., 2018. *Effective Ecological Monitoring.* CSIRO publishing, Clayton South, Australia. [🔗](#) <https://doi.org/10.1071/9781486308934>
- Stephenson, P.J., Mansourian, S., Borges, P.A.V., Correa, D.C.V., Polanco Fernández, et al., 2025. *Opportunities and Challenges for Monitoring Ecosystem Restoration in Protected and Conserved Areas IUCN WCPA Technical Note No. 24.* IUCN WCPA & IUCN SSC Species Monitoring Specialist Group, IUCN, Gland, Switzerland. [🔗](#)
- Tucker, G., Fasham, M., Hill, D., Shewry, M., Shaw, P. and Wade, M., 2005. Planning a programme. *Handbook of Biodiversity Methods: Survey Evaluation and Monitoring*, pp. 6-64. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK. [🔗](#)
- World Bank, 2004. *Ten Steps to a Results-Based Monitoring and Evaluation System: A Handbook For Development Practitioners.* (Kusek, J.Z. & Rist, R.C.). World Bank, Washington DC, USA. [🔗](#)
- UNDP - United Nations Development Programme, 2009. *Handbook on Planning, Monitoring and Evaluating for Development Results.* UNDP, New York, USA. [🔗](#)
- USAID - United States Agency for International Development, 2016. *Defining Outcomes and Indicators for Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning in USAID Biodiversity Programming.* USAID, Washington DC, USA. [🔗](#)

> Guidelines for developing monitoring plans and choosing indicators (corporate sector focused)

- IBAT, 2021. *Species Threat Abatement and Restoration (STAR) data layer. Business User Guidance.* IBAT Alliance. [🔗](#)
- IFC – International Finance Corporation, 2012. *Performance Standard 6: Biodiversity Conservation and Sustainable Management of Living Natural Resources.* IFC, Washington DC, USA. [🔗](#)
- SBTN, 2024. *Corporate Manual for Setting Science-Based Targets for Nature.* Science-Based Targets Network. [🔗](#)
- Stephenson, P.J. 2021. *A Review of Biodiversity Data Needs and Monitoring Protocols for the Offshore Wind Energy Sector in the Baltic Sea and North Sea.* Renewables Grid Initiative, Berlin, Germany. [🔗](#)
- Stephenson, P.J. 2024. *Monitoring Biodiversity at Sea: Discussion paper on advancing standardised biodiversity monitoring for Nature-Positive offshore wind development.* GINGR Navigator No. 2. Global Initiative for Nature, Grids and Renewables (Renewables Grid Initiative & IUCN), Berlin, Germany and Gland, Switzerland. [🔗](#)
- Natural Capital Coalition, 2016. *Natural Capital Protocol.* NCC, London, UK. [🔗](#)
- Stephenson, P.J. and Carbone, G., 2021. *Guidelines for Planning and Monitoring Corporate Biodiversity Performance.* IUCN, Gland, Switzerland. [🔗](#)
- TNFD, 2023. *Recommendations of the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures.* [🔗](#)

> Methodological articles relating to monitoring design and indicator choice

- Addison, P.F., Stephenson, P.J., Bull, J.W., Carbone, G., Burgman, M., *et al.*, 2020. Bringing sustainability to life: A framework to guide biodiversity indicator development for business performance management. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(8), pp.3303-3313. [↗](#)
- Buckingham, K., Ray, S., Granizo, C.G., Toh, L., Stolle, F., *et al.*, 2019. *The Road to Restoration: A Guide to Identifying Priorities and Indicators for Monitoring Forest and Landscape Restoration*. FAO and WRI, Rome and London. [↗](#)
- Burgess, N.D., Ali, N., Bedford, J., Bholá, N., Brooks, S., *et al.*, 2024. Global metrics for terrestrial biodiversity. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 49(1), pp.673-709. [↗](#)
- Jones, J.P., Asner, G.P., Butchart, S.H. and Karanth, K.U., 2013. The 'why', 'what' and 'how' of monitoring for conservation. *Key Topics in Conservation Biology 2*, pp.329-343. J. Wiley & Sons, London, UK. [↗](#)
- Lindenmayer, D.B. and Likens, G.E., 2009. Adaptive monitoring. *Trends in Ecology and Evolution*, 24(9), pp.482-486. [↗](#)
- Mansourian, S. and Stephenson, P.J., 2023. Exploring challenges and lessons for monitoring forest landscape restoration. *Current Landscape Ecology Reports*, 8(4), pp.159-170. [↗](#)
- Stephenson, P.J., 2019. The Holy Grail of biodiversity conservation management: monitoring impact in projects and project portfolios. *Perspectives in Ecology and Conservation*, 17(4), pp.182-192. [↗](#)
- Wauchope, H.S., Amano, T., Geldmann, J., Johnston, A., Simmons, B.I., *et al.*, 2021. Evaluating impact using time-series data. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 36(3), pp.196-205. [↗](#)

> Methodological articles relating to data standards, statistically-sound survey design and the use of statistics in surveying populations

- Bailey, L.L., MacKenzie, D.I. and Nichols, J.D., 2014. Advances and applications of occupancy models. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 5(12), pp.1269-1279. [↗](#)
- Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG), 2020. *Standards*. [↗](#)
- Buckland, S.T., Anderson, D.R., Burnham, K.P., Laake, J.L., Borchers, D.L. and Thomas, L., 2001. *Introduction to Distance Sampling: Estimating Abundance of Biological Populations*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK. [↗](#)
- Buckland, S.T., Rexstad, E.A., Marques, T.A., and Oedekoven, C.S., 2015. *Distance Sampling: Methods and Applications*. Springer, New York, USA. [↗](#)
- Doser, J.W., Finley, A.O., Kéry, M. and Zipkin, E.F., 2022. spOccupancy: An R package for single species, multi species, and integrated spatial occupancy models. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 13(8), pp.1670-1678. [↗](#)
- GBIF – Global Biodiversity Information Facility, 2025. *Data standards*. [↗](#)
- Greenwood, J.J.D and Robinson, R.A., 2006. Principles of sampling. *Ecological Census Techniques, second edition*, pp. 11-86. Cambridge University Press. [↗](#)
- Hector, A., 2021. *The New Statistics with R: An Introduction for Biologists*. Oxford University Press. [↗](#)
- Lohr, S.L., 2021. *Sampling: Design and Analysis*. Chapman and Hall/CRC, New York, USA. [↗](#)
- MacKenzie, D.I., Nichols, J.D., Royle, J.A., Pollock, K.H., Bailey, L. and Hines, J.E., 2017. *Occupancy Estimation and Modeling: Inferring Patterns and Dynamics of Species Occurrence*. Elsevier, London, UK. [↗ https://doi.org/10.1016/C2012-0-01164-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/C2012-0-01164-7)
- MacKenzie, D.I. and Reardon, J.T., 2013. Occupancy methods for conservation management. *Biodiversity monitoring and conservation: Bridging the gap between global commitment and local action*, pp.248-264. John Wiley & Sons, London, UK. [↗](#)
- Reynolds, J.H., 2012. An overview of statistical considerations in long-term monitoring. *Design and Analysis of Long-term Ecological Monitoring Studies*, pp.23-53. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK. [↗](#)
- Schleicher, J., Eklund, J., D. Barnes, M., Geldmann, J., Oldekop, J.A. and Jones, J.P., 2020. Statistical matching for conservation science. *Conservation Biology*, 34(3), pp.538-549. [↗](#)
- TEAM Network. 2011a. *Terrestrial Vertebrate Protocol Implementation Manual, v. 3.1*. Tropical Ecology, Assessment and Monitoring Network, Center for Applied Biodiversity Science, Conservation International, Arlington, VA, USA. [↗](#)
- TEAM Network. 2011b. *TEAM Network Sampling Design Guidelines, Version 1.0*. Tropical Ecology, Assessment and Monitoring Network, Center for Applied Biodiversity Science, Conservation International, Arlington, VA, USA. [↗](#)
- Thilan, A.P., Peterson, E., Menéndez, P., Caley, J., Drovandi, C., *et al.*, 2024. Bayesian design methods for improving the effectiveness of ecosystem monitoring. *Environmental and Ecological Statistics*, 31, pp.893-919. [↗](#)
- Welsh, A.H., Lindenmayer, D.B. and Donnelly, C.F., 2013. Fitting and interpreting occupancy models. *PloS One*, 8(1), p.e52015. [↗](#)
- Yoccoz, N.G., Nichols, J.D. and Boulinier, T., 2001. Monitoring of biological diversity in space and time. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 16(8), pp.446-453. [↗](#)

> Articles on Indigenous and local knowledge and citizen science

- Danielsen, F., Jensen, P.M., Burgess, N.D., Altamirano, R., Alviola, P.A., Andrianandrasana, H., Brashares, J.S., Burton, A.C., Coronado, I., Corpuz, N., Enghoff, M. *et al.*, 2014. A multicountry assessment of tropical resource monitoring by local communities. *BioScience*, 64(3), pp.236-251. [🔗](#)
- Izquierdo-Tort, S., Alatorre, A., Arroyo-Geral, P., Shapiro-Garza, E., Naime, J. and Dupras, J., 2024. Exploring local perceptions and drivers of engagement in biodiversity monitoring among participants in payments for ecosystem services schemes in southeastern Mexico. *Conservation Biology*, 38, p.e14282. [🔗](#)
- Jennings, L., Anderson, T., Martinez, A., Sterling, R., Chavez, D.D., *et al.*, 2023. Applying the 'CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance' to ecology and biodiversity research. *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 7(10), pp.1547-1551. [🔗](#)
- McElwee, P., Fernández-Llamazares, Á., Aumeeruddy-Thomas, Y., Babai, D., Bates, P., *et al.*, 2020. Working with Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) in large-scale ecological assessments: Reviewing the experience of the IPBES Global Assessment. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 57(9), pp.1666-1676. [🔗](#)
- UNEP. 2019. *Global Environment Outlook—GEO-6: Healthy Planet, Healthy People*. United Nations Environment Programme, Nairobi, Kenya. [🔗](#)

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For more information see here [🔗](#)
or contact SpeciesMonitoringSG@gmail.com.

